

EHMA 2024.

Shaping and managing
innovative health ecosystems

5-7 June 2024 - Bucharest, Romania

ABSTRACT BOOK

Institutul Național de Management
al Serviciilor de Sănătate

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) is a not-for-profit membership organisation. Active since 1982, our vision is excellent health management for a healthy Europe.

We support the spread of knowledge on effective health management. Our actions focus on health management capacity and capabilities and aim to support the successful implementation of health policy and practice. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, with a European and global reach. Through our efforts, we make a difference across Europe to improve health for all citizens.

We are open to all those committed to improving health and healthcare. We play a crucial role in engaging with the full European health management ecosystem. We are a highly accessible and well-established place where people can debate and engage in issues that affect them, where they feel they can advocate for change, and find solutions. Through our members and networks, we reach local, regional, national, and international levels.

About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The European Health Management Conference 2024

EHMA 2024 is the 29th edition of our Annual Conference. This year's conference theme 'Shaping and managing innovative health ecosystems' encompasses the entire spectrum of health megatrends. From the digital transformation of healthcare systems and services, to the ever-growing importance of sustainability, and the evolving skill sets required by the healthcare workforce, we aim to explore how the health sector is adapting to these changes.

We emphasise an ecosystem approach, promoting collaboration among stakeholders. Our aim is to facilitate dialogue on how different health care actors can work together and leverage each other's strengths to drive innovation and address pressing challenges.

Acknowledgements

EHMA acknowledge the expert guidance of the Abstract Reviewers for assessing and selecting the 297 health management research abstracts received as part of the Call for Abstracts.

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Valuation and perception of the costs of climate change on health

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Context: Climate change affects our societies and lives through our economies, our livelihoods, and our health. Economic losses of climate change are estimated at \$23 trillion, largely through externalities due to premature mortality, health-care expenditure, and health-related work losses. Even if there are established methods to quantify the health economic burden, there is limited information on how people perceive this information. The current study aimed to examine different health cost evaluation methods and observe perceptions of stakeholders in the climate change context. The current study aimed to examine how to evaluate the health care costs and the external costs of climate change by analysing different calculation methods and observing its perceptions among experts, policy- and decisionmakers and non-governmental (NGO) sector representatives.

Methods: The participatory research approach of the World Café with 41 participants of a workshop was applied to explore four topics associated with valuing the costs of climate change: (1) "Actual health-care cost or willingness to pay – what is better indicator of costs?", (2) "How cost-effective are mitigation and adaptation measures?", (3) "How external costs concept could be integrated into policies?", (4) "How to make public better understand the costs of climate change?" The data were analysed following an inductive approach. For analysis of recorded data, we established a matrix that included the questions and responses from the representatives. In content analysis we summarised the identified main themes (ethics, methods, data, communication, holistic approach, political agenda and best practice) and subthemes.

Results: Despite the willingness to pay approach being widely applied, many experts see direct health-care costs as a more explicit indicator of costs; however, this might underestimate the full social costs. The participants experienced difficulties accepting and understanding cost estimates indicating very high externalities as percentages of GDP. The cost-effectiveness of mitigation and adaptation measures was challenged by the query that costs incurring now, but benefits happening later as it can be with building bike lanes or dams. The policies should favour environmentally friendly activities as making cycling more convenient in the cities with the health benefits in monetary terms while limiting car driving. Public could better understand the costs of climate change with a tool mapping how solutions influence different sectors and showing monetarised benefits for health.

Discussion: Estimating the price tag of climate change on human health is not critical but challenging. The methods, how experts communicate, and present numbers prove to be crucial both for politicians when setting up political agenda and building trust towards public. During the World Café discussions, it was suggested that using stories can be more effective when communicating with the public. The need for well-presented science and data quality was stressed as a crucial theme by all participants. Especially for some experts it was more critical to have any relevant existing data. For others it was about having updated data and that packaging data is right so it can be used in decision- and policy making. Enhancing health, climate change and external costs literacy among the public, policymakers, and the media is essential for better understanding the comprehensive effects of policies on environmental burdens.